

ADEQUATE TRANSLATION

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Annotation An adequate translation is really difficult because it requires a lot of knowledge about source languages and target languages. This article explains the main characters of adequate translation. Furthermore, there are various methods that can help to make a translation more satisfactory and adequate.

Key words: translation accuracy, source language, target language, lexical analysis, language structures.

An adequate translation can only be that translation, which accurately conveys not only the meaning, but also the expressive - stylistic features of the original. Translation must perform certain functions: informative, informative, aesthetic, etc.

Translation adequacy requires a precise and accurate transfer of the meaning from the source language into the target one.

Problems of adequate translation: As an example of Uzbek and English languages

We can compare Uzbek and English adequate translation. For example, "She is very busy nowadays. She has a lot on her plate because of her work and study." In English this sounds natural. So, while translating these sentences the translator must be careful and pay attention to lexical and stylistic meaning of sentences, because Uzbek language's lexical meaning is quite different from English language's. Otherwise people can translate it into Uzbek like "U bu oralar juda band. Uning likopchasida ko'p narsa bor iahi tufayli" and it would be wrong translation. Because here are several points that we should consider before translation. "Have a lot on the plate" this is a phrase and means "juda ishi ko'p" in Uzbek. So correct translation should be as "U bu oralar juda band. Uning ishi tufayli qiladigan ishlari ko'p"

We can make different mistakes when we translate from English into Uzbek or vice versa. Mistakes in the translation can be classified in several groups of translator competence. When a translator misunderstands some words and finds it difficult to get the text, can not comprehend the logical structure of the book. When a translator does not understand the difference of the language structure and speech and does not know how to transform phrases into the target language. Sometimes a translator may misunderstand the author and his intentions and may fail to identify the author's evaluation in the text of the source language. Finally, a translator may choose the wrong word due to insufficient competence in the target language. Every translator can come across to such kind of challenges. And it is common and ordinary. Meaning is that we do not have to be afraid of such kind of sentences.

Any translation is a responsibility because a translator creates his text in the eye of a target-text reader. In the first place, the translator should show the way the author understands the novel. A translator should make some preliminary analysis to 'feel' the text. The text should be equally understandable and equally vague and complicated as the writer planned it to be. This principal task of a translator is to choose exact words and stylistic means in the target text to show all the beauty of the source text. For example while translating texts from English into Uzbek or vice versa, it is difficult to keep the all the sentence original. However we can change them little bit and make beautiful sentences.

The main task of the translation is to reflect peculiarities of the source language with the possible 'techniques' of the target language. In my article, I pay a lot of attention to lexical and stylistic analysis of the translation, because in combination they help to create an adequate translation. If any translator uses some special sources of the target language, even if it does not coincide with the structure of the source text, it can solve or even avoid some translation problems. When a translator takes into consideration the whole context of the novel he is translating from the point of the source text, he will create an adequate translation. Besides, source language understanding plays a major role. Exactly understanding all differences between Uzbek language and English language is compulsory. The better the translator understands the source language and the author's language, the more natural for him to create the translation, which could be an adequate version of the original text.

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